

Comparative Study of Two Economically Important Species of *Hibiscus* L. (Malvaceae)

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Hibiscus* L. Malvaceae comprises several species of taxonomic, economic and medicinal importance, many of which exhibit close morphological resemblance, leading to difficulties in accurate identification. Among them, *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. are widely cultivated species that differ in their utilitarian value but share several external similarities. The present study aims to provide, a comparative taxonomic assessment of these two species based on morphological and anatomical characters. Fresh specimen was collected from the Marathwada region of Maharashtra, India and examined using standard taxonomic and anatomical techniques. Morphological observations were recorded for vegetative characters, while anatomical investigations including transverse sections of Root, Stem, Leaf and Petiole Prepared using double staining technique. The findings highlight the importance of integrating anatomical characters with external morphology in resolving taxonomic ambiguities within the genus *Hibiscus* L. The present work contributes to regional floristic documentation and provides a structural basis for accurate identification of economically important *Hibiscus* L. Species.

Keywords: *Hibiscus cannabinus* L., *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., Anatomy, Taxonomy, Marathwada, Maharashtra.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Hibiscus* L. belonging to the family Malvaceae comprises over 300 species distributed mainly in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. Species of *Hibiscus* are well known for their economic, medicinal, ornamental and industrial importance. Several members of the genus are widely cultivated in India while many others occur in wild or semi wild conditions, contributing significantly to regional floristic diversity. Despite their importance, taxonomic delimitations within the genus remains challenging due to overlapping morphological characters among closely related species.

Hibiscus cannabinus L. (Kenaf) and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. (Roselle) are two prominent species cultivated across different agro-climatic regions of India.

Hibiscus cannabinus L. is primarily valued for its bast fibers, whereas *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. is extensively used for edible calyces and medicinal properties. Although these species differ in their utilitarian roles, they share several external morphological features, particularly during vegetative stages, which often leads to misidentification in field conditions. The Marathwada region of Maharashtra represents a semi-arid zone where both *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. cultivated varied ecological conditions. However, detailed comparative studies emphasizing anatomical attributes of these species from this regions are limited. The present investigation aims to undertake a comparative taxonomic study of *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. and *Hibiscus*

sabdariffa L. based on morphological and anatomical characters, with the objective of identifying reliable diagnostic features that support accurate identification and contribute to regional systematic documentation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Healthy and mature specimens of *Hibiscus cannabinus* L., and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L., were collected from cultivated fields in the dist. Beed, Dharashiv and Latur from Marathwada region of Maharashtra, India. The Plants were identified using standard and taxonomic literature voucher specimen were prepared and preserved for future reference.

Morphological Study:

Characters	<i>Hibiscus cannabinus</i> L.	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.
Root	Tap root, Branched	Tap root ,Branched
Stem	Erect, Branched, shrub, woody at base, 2 m tall, Prickly and with line of hairs Green.	Erect, cylindrical, Branched, shrub, woody at base, 2-3.5 m tall, hairy, red in color,
Leaf	Green 5-15 cm across, variable in shape, normally deeply lobed, 3-7 lobes, lanceolate, dentate-serrate, acute, sometimes entire, simple, petiole up to 20 cm long, hairy, stipules narrowly linear to filiform, 5-8 mm long caduceus	Green with red veins, alternate, lower leaves are undivided or simple, ovateor nearly round while upper leaves are lobed, 3-7 palmately lobes or lanceolate, margin serrated, 3-15 cm length, petiole red, 10-15 cm long.
Inflorescence	Solitary Axillary	Solitary Axillary
Flower	7-10 cm across, solitary, axillary, short pedicel, blooms appear in leaf axis, stout, white yellow or purple, when white or yellow center is dark purple or maroon, twisted, pentamerous, complete, cyclic, hermaphrodite, actinomorphic, superior ovary, 7-10 bracteoles, 8-10 mm long slightly adnate to the base of calyx	5-10 cm across, solitary, axillary, born at leaf axis, short pedicel, complete, cyclic, Pentamerous, hermaphrodite, actinomorphic, superior ovary, Pale Yellow or cream yellow petals, pubescent, dark crimson or maroon at the center, twisted, 7-12 linear, red bracteoles surrounding the base of the calyx,
Calyx	1.5-2 cm long, lobes triangular, acuminate, with gland at the base on the outer side, 5 sepals, valvate, gamosepalous, Green.	5 sepals, valvate, gamosepalous, red, fleshy, long acuminate
Corolla	3-4 cm long, Pale or cream Yellow, with purple base, 5 Petals, polypetalous, twisted	4-6 cm long, cream yellow, dark crimson or red spot at the base, 5 petals, polypetalous, twisted.
Androecium	Monadelphous Numerous stamens filaments fused together to form staminal tube that surround the style, anthers monothecous, reniform, yellow.	Monadelphous Numerous stamens with filaments united into a central staminal column, anthers yellow.
Gynoecium	The style 17-23 mm is long and passes through the staminal tube divided into five free, capitate (head like) stigmas, pentacarpellary, Pentalocular, superior ovary.	A single, 5 branched style with capitate stigma.
Fruit	Capsule, ovoid to cylindrical, beaked and pubescent, contains 18-20 or more seeds.	Five valved conical, beaked capsule, 1.5-2 cm long
Seeds	Sub-reniform to triangular, brown to dark gray.	Brown to dark gray , kidney shaped

Hibiscus cannabinus L.

Hibiscus sabdariffa L.

Fig- Root, Stem, Leaves, Flower, Fruit & Seeds of *Hibiscus cannabinus L.*

Fig- Root, Stem, Leaf, Flower, Fruit & seeds of *Hibiscus sabdariffa L.*

Anatomical Study: To study Anatomy double staining method was used. This method is particularly useful in comparative anatomical studies as it allows effective distinction between mechanical, conducting and storage tissue, by supporting detailed anatomical interpretation and taxonomic assessment.

Process: Transverse sections of root, stem, leaf, petiole were taken from preserved plant material. After that sections were kept in safranin for few minutes then rinse with water until excess stain removed. Then passed into alcohol grades (15%, 30%, 50%, & 70%). Then it kept into fast green stain for 2 min, then again passed into 90% and Pure alcohol

respectively. The kept in xylol for 1min and later mounted in DPX. And observed under microscope.

Hibiscus cannabinus L.

T.S of Root: Outer Periderm is noticed, made up of Phellem and Phellderm. Followed by the darker, denser circle are xylem vessels surrounding regions less prominent than xylem is phloem surrounded by parenchyma or cortex.

T.S of Stem: The outermost single layer epidermis is present. Below the epidermis, cortex is present consist of multiple layers of Parenchymatous cells. Below the

cortex endodermis is present. Followed by xylem located towards the center and phloem located outwards from the xylem. Cambium is present in between xylem and phloem. At the center pith is present made up of loosely packed parenchyma cells.

T.S of Leaf: The structure includes outer epidermis, which is single layered and covered with cuticle. Followed by epidermis mesophyll tissues and present i.e. elongated palisade located beneath the upper epidermis. Below the palisade layer spongy layer of irregular cells are present with large air spaces. Followed by mesophyll vascular bundle is present which contains xylem and phloem.

T.S of Root

T.S of Stem

T.S of Leaf

T.S of Petiole

T.S of Petiole: The outer single layered is present, covered with a cuticle. Beneath the epidermis, layers of collenchyma present. Followed by cortex consists of thin walled Parenchymatous cells. Followed by vascular bundles present in ring form, xylem located towards the inner side and phloem on the outer side. At the center large Parenchymatous cells are present as ground tissue.

Hibiscus sabdariffa L.

T.S of Root:

The transverse section shows the outermost layer is replaced by periderm consisting of phellem, phellogen and phelloderm. Inner to periderm lies secondary phloem, followed by a continuous ring of vascular cambium. The cambium produces secondary phloem towards the outside. The secondary xylem forms large wide shaped sectors containing vessels, fibres and xylem parenchyma. Medullary rays are radially arranged parenchymatous tissues extending through xylem and phloem. the central region is occupied by parenchymatous pith.

T. S of Stem:

The outermost region periderm followed by cortex, secondary phloem occurs beneath the cortex and appears in patches while primary phloem is crushed. A

continuous vascular cambium ring separates the phloem from the xylem. Extensive secondary xylem is formed on the inner side of the cambium, consisting of vessels, fibres and xylem parenchyma arranged in radial rows. Medullary rays are seen as radial parenchymatous pith meant for storage.

T. S of Leaf:

Leaf section shows upper and lower epidermis carrying trichome and covered smooth cuticle. The lamina has mesophyll. Mesophyll is dorsiventral with upper palisade formed of one row of radially elongated columnar cells with almost straight anticlinal walls. It is interrupted by collenchyma in midrib region. The spongy tissue is formed of 5-6 rows of thin walled more or less rounded chlorenchymatous with subepidermal collenchyma. Cortex followed by endodermis formed of thin walled parenchymatous cells. vascular bundle is replaced by large strands with xylem to the adaxial side and phloem to the abaxial side.

T. S of Petiole :

Outermost an epidermis covered with glandular and stellate trichomes are abundant. Cortex is formed of 1-3 rows of chlorenchyma cells. Followed by 2-3 rows of thick collenchymatous cells. Rest of the cortex is formed of 3-6 rows of parenchymatous cells.

T.S of Root showing Periderm, cortex & Pith

T.S of Stem showing Periderm, cortex & pith

T.S of Leaf Unstained and Stained

T.S of petiole

Hairs on Epidermis

The endodermis is distinct consists of axially elongated parenchymatous cells surrounding the pericycle, pericycle is formed groups of lignified fibers. The vascular tissues is formed of continuous ring of collateral vascular bundle. The pith is formed by wide parenchymatous cells.

Uses:

Hibiscus cannabinus L.

It is fiber yielding plant widely cultivated for its strong bast fibers. The fibers are extensively used in the manufacture of ropes, twines, sacks, cordage and coarse textiles. Due to its high tensile strength and biodegradability, kenaf fibers are also utilized in paper pulp production and as eco-friendly alternatives in packaging materials. Seeds are used to produce edible oil, in cooking, roasted or ground in flour. Leaves are commonly eaten in india (especially Andhra Pradesh) and parts of Africa, used in soups, salads and Pickles.

Extract from leaves and flowers reduce inflammatory markers and possess high antioxidant activity. Leaf infusions are used to treat cough, bronchitis and as a digestive aid. Also used as livestock feed. In recent years, *Hibiscus cannabinus L.* has gained attention for its application in Bio-composites, insulation boards and sustainable construction materials. Plant contributes to soil improvement when used in crop rotation systems.

Hibiscus sabdariffa L.

The leaves used to make dishes like chutneys and bhaji which are eaten with sorghum (jowar) or millet (bajra) flat bread. The calyces are used for beverages,

herbal drinks, fermented drinks, wine, jams, jellied confectionaries etc. It's been widely used in local medicines. Medicinally the plant exhibits antimicrobial, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammetory, hepatoprotective Properties. Calyces are used as antihypertensive (Helps lower blood pressure), antioxidant (rich in anthocyanin and phenolics). In India also used in traditional medicine to treat fever, liver disorders, digestive problem and urinary tract infections by preparing decoction from seed and calyaes due to its high content of flavonoids, vitamin C, Organic acids. Extracts are utilized in pharmaceutical formulation and herbal supplements, for cardiovascular, metabolic health. It is one of the most important species grown commercially as a fiber plant. Calyx pigment (anthocyanine) used as natural food colorant and also used as cosmetic ingredient. Seeds oil used in making of soaps, cosmetics, industrial lubricants (limited use). Plant residues are used as organic manure. Leaves are used as fodder for livestock.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The comparative study of *Hibiscus cannabinus L.* and *Hibiscus sabdariffa L.* revealed both shared and distinctive morphological and anatomical characters typical of the family Malvaceae. Morphological observations indicated differences in plant height, stem surface, leaf shape and petiole length, colors or pigments of plant which are useful for preliminary field identification, however these characters alone may not always be reliable due to environmental

influence. Anatomical observations provide more reliable diagnostic features. Both species exhibited typical dicot root anatomy with exarch xylem, while variations in cortical width and xylem vessel frequency were evident. In *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. Stem anatomy showed a single layered epidermis collenchymatous hypodermis and ring arranged conjoint, collateral and open vascular bundles, However, In *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. the transverse section of stem showed secondary growth. This difference may be influenced by geographical and climatic conditions rather than being strictly species-specific. Leaf anatomy was dorsiventral with a single palisade layer and multilayered spongy mesophyll compactness and intercellular spaces. Petiole anatomy further supported species differentiation through variation in vascular bundle number and arc-shaped arrangement. Overall, the integration of anatomical and morphological characters enhances taxonomic clarity and reduces ambiguity in species identification. The anatomical differences observed in the present study provide dependable diagnostic markers for distinguishing *Hibiscus cannabinus* L. and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. contributing to systematic studies and regional floristic documentation.

CONCLUSION

The present study establishes the significance of anatomical characters as dependable tools for taxonomic delimitation within the genus *Hibiscus*. Studied species provide clear evidence that internal features offer greater stability and diagnostic reliability than external morphology alone. The integration of anatomical observations with traditional taxonomic approaches strengthens species identification and contributes to resolving systematic ambiguities within closely related taxa. The findings of this study enrich regional botanical knowledge of *Hibiscus* Species from Marathwada and provide a scientific baseline for future taxonomic and floristic investigations.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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